

Assessment for Learning: A Catalyst for Redefining Educational Needs

SUB TOPIC: Teacher Training and Support for Effective Remedial Instruction

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Abstract

Paper explores the need of assessment for learning due to changing nature of educational goals and also the relationship between assessment and teaching learning for the quality improvement in the schools of Delhi. How different teaching strategies for assessment for learning can help to bridge the learning deficits and to achieve the learning outcomes in upper primary classes?

Four classroom strategies are discussed in the paper for assessment for learning: 1. Use of questioning. 2. Peer feedback. 3. Student's self-assessment. 4. Formative use of summative assessment. For example different strategies for the Peer feedback are: a. two stars and a wish. b. Plus Minus and what next? c. Warm and cool feedback. d. Traffic lights. e. Using models and exemplar. f. De Bono's Hats.

Reflection activities of peer assessment, self-assessment and group assessment and How to set the targets using SMART acronym are also in exploration pipe line and are also being practiced by the investigator to check their effectiveness in real classroom situation.

Further few strategies to promote the formative use of tests will also be explored by the investigator: 1. making formative use of state tests like: Base line tests to find out the learning levels of the students in all Delhi government schools. 2. Making formative use of classroom testing. 3. Timings of tests: Tests before the lesson, midway tests and after the tests strategies are also in the pipe line. At the end paper explains preparing the test by the students using traffic lights. So in all paper is regarding the exploration of possibilities in the assessment for learning strategies to bridge the learning deficits, which can be implemented in Upper primary classes' of Delhi schools.

Keywords: *Assessment for learning, teaching processes, classroom testing, evaluation.*

Introduction and rationale:

No detention policy, Right to Education, Continuous and comprehensive evaluation pattern (CCE), midday meal, Menstrual Health scheme (Kishori yojana) etc. No doubt reduced the dropout rate of children in the schools and increased the enrolment in the classrooms, classes are inflated and over loaded with children, but lack of infrastructures, shortage of teachers, low quality of education in the schools are the issues which have come up over the period and need urgent attention. For sustainable development we need to address these issues on priority basis. The last decade has witnessed a growing recognition of the need for significant changes in educational assessment practices like implementation of CCE and then scraping of CCE in secondary classes. The calls for reform are directed at classroom assessment practices at the moment. Two major factors have contributed to the demands for assessment reform.

- 1. Changing nature of educational goals**
- 2. The relationship between assessment and the teaching learning.**

NCERT an advocate of outcome based education argues persuasively that educators must broaden their target to include outcomes that relate to lifelong learning. Given these recommendations, many states have focused their attention on identifying important "exit outcomes" or learning outcomes. For example Directorate of Education (DOE) Delhi launched programme "Chunuti" and students were divided into groups according to their learning levels. Although the educators have acknowledged the importance of outcomes like those listed by NCERT or Directorate of Education Delhi they have quickly recognised that current assessments do not adequately address these outcomes. For the most part tests require students to recall or recognise fragmented and isolated bits of information. They rarely ask

students to apply that information, and they almost never require students to exhibit proficiencies in the higher forms of cognition such as complex reasoning and self-directedness.

Tests we do use are unable to measure what should be the hallmark of a “thinking” curriculum: the cultivation of student’s ability to apply skill and knowledge to real world problems. These shortcomings make it clear that new approaches to assessment are needed if we are to satisfactorily assess students’ ability to meet the lifelong learning standards, demanding content standards and outcomes that are the centrepiece of the plan to make the education system better. A second factor contributing to the need for assessment reform involves the relationship between assessment and the processes of teaching and learning. The need for assessment practices to enhance the learning and teaching processes.

Assessment for learning is the process of seeking and interpreting evidence for use by learners and their teachers to decide where the learners are in their learning. Where they need to go and how best to get there (assessment reform group (UK 2002) assessment for learning is also known as formative assessment and assessment of learning as summative assessment. Assessment activities associated with summative assessment result in an evaluation of student achievement: for example promotion to next level on the basis of allocation of a letter or numerical grade. Activities associated with formative assessment do not result in an evaluation. Paper presents the case studies findings of these studies help us to understand that why assessment for learning?

Methodology:

The paper is based on two case studies. Post test Self assessment activity after the first term exam was given to the students of class X in case study 1. Post test self assessment activity after the third periodic test was given to class IX students in case study-2. Data was collected and is presented in tabular form. Strategies were designed according to the need of the classroom. Self assessment activity was used during both the cases mentioned in the paper.

Scope for further study:

1. More strategies can be designed in different subjects.
2. Different activities for peer learning, group learning, self- learning can also be designed.
3. Impact of these activities on the achievement of the students can also be studied.

Limitations:

1. The study presents only two case studies .
2. Study is limited to GNCT of Delhi.
3. Both case studies are based on either on high scoring or low scoring.
4. Subject taken in the study is mathematics of class X and IX only.

Review of Literature:

Studies about the assessment for learning as a means of improving classroom learning in countries like the UK Australia and New Zealand is being carried out in different ways with the intention that only assessment of learning that too pen paper form sometimes not helping to motivate the learner and reduces the interest of the learner in studies.

Students have the ability to increase their motivation for learning and their academic achievement (Chappuis, 2005; Stiggins 2007).

Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) Early Grade Reading Assessment in India.

Case study school -1

SSS (Senior Secondary School)

A sample from a School was selected, the students who scored more than 80% marks in Mid-Term exam in class X session 2017-2018. Data of re-evaluation of 78 answer scripts is given below.

Abbreviations:

1. Question Number - (Q. No.)
2. Not Attempted - (N/A)
3. Wrong answer - (W/A)
4. Identification - ID

5. + - Re-attempt, e.g. 2+1 same question was attempted two times and awarded marks first time 2 and second time 1. Question carries only 1 mark.

Table-1

(I.Marker) class X Mathematics SA-I 2017-2018.

S. No.	Section	Student ID	Q. No.1	Q. No.2	Q. No.3	Q. No.4	Q. No.5	Q. No.6
1	I	246403	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	I	236357	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	I	196003	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	I	236521	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	I	246411	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	I	318342	1	1	1	1	1	1
7	I	330585	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	I	236186	1	1	1	1	1	1
9	I	236368	1	1	1	1	1	1
10	H	234675	1	1	1	1	1	1
11	H	235964	1	1	1	1	1	1
12	H	235972	1	1	1	1	1	1
13	H	236344	1	1	1	1	1	1
14	H	236434	1	1	1	1	1	1
15	H	246394	1	1	1	1	1	1
16	H	246520	1	1	1	1	1	1
17	H	246526	1	1	1	1	1	1
18	H	246531	1	1	1	1	1	N/A
19	H	296680	1	1	1	1	1	1
20	L	320234	1	1	1	1	1	2
21	L	293658	1	1	1/2	1/2	1	1
22	L	184398	1	1	1	1	1	1
23	L	184345	1	1	1/2	1	1	1/2
24	C	178688	1	1	1	1	1	1
25	D	224761	1	1	1	1/2	1	1
26	D	232533	1	1	1	1	1	1
27	K	189962	1	1	1	1	1	1
28	K	294094	1	1	2	3	N/A	1
29	K	294059	1	1	1	1	1	1
30	K	192360	1	2+1	1	1	1	1
31	K	192102	1	1	1	1	1	1
32	K	190030	1	1+1	1	1	1	1
33	K	192072	1	1	1	1	1	1
34	K	191436	1	1	1	N/A	1	1
35	K	191418	1	1	1	1	1	1
36	G	219389	1	1	1	1	1	1
37	G	296701	1	1	1	1	N/A	1
38	G	235386	1	1	1	1	1	1
39	G	235866	1	1	1	1	1	1
40	G	235371	1	1	1	1	N/A	1
41	G	296688	1	1	1	1	1	1
42	G	246621	1	1	1	1	1	1
43	G	235177	1	1	1	1	1	1
44	G	211031	1	1	1	1	1	1
45	G	246682	1	1	1	1	1	1
46	J	246537	1	1	1	1	1	1
47	J	246638	1	1	1	1	1	1+2
48	J	246641	1	1	1	1	1	1
49	J	248663	1	1	1	1	1	N/A
50	J	248684	1	1	1	1	1	2
51	J	246687	1	1	1	1	N/A	1
52	J	314615	1	1	1	N/A	1	1
53	J	311090	1	1	1	1	1	1
54	J	324098	1	1	1	1	1	2
55	J	324124	1	1	1	1	1	2
56	A	121684	1	1	1	1	1	1
57	A	040680	1	1	1	1.5	2	2

58	A	122910	1	1	1	2	2	2
59	A	124259	1	1	1	2	2	2
60	A	234115	1	1	1	1	2+2	2
61	A	310089	1	1	1	1	2	2
62	B	244443	1	1	1	2	2	2
63	B	244153	1	1	1	N/A	2	2
64	E	233533	1	1	1	1	1	1
65	E	233859	1	1	1	N/A	1	1
66	E	233963	1	1	1	1	1	1
67	E	234687	1	1	1	1	1	1
68	E	233852	1	1	1	1	N/A	1
69	F	234735	1	1	1	N/A	N/A	1
70	F	219858	1	1	1	1	1	1
71	F	219842	1	1	1	1	1	1
72	F	199294	1	1	1	1	1	1
73	C	178781	1	1	1/2	1/2	1	1
74	C	119802	1	1	1/2	1/2	1	1
75	C	015915	1	1/2	N/A	N/A	1	1
76	C	168700	1	1	1	1	1	1
77	C	175439	1	½+1	1/2	1	1	1
78	C	178681	1	1	1	1	1	1

(Source of the data is primary collected by the author)

Table 2

(2 Marker) class X Mathematics SA-1 2017-2018

S. No.	Section	Student ID	Q. No.7	Q. No.8	Q. No.9	Q. No.10	Q. No.11	Q. No.12
1	I	246403	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	I	236357	2	2	2	2	2	2
3	I	196003	2	2	2	1.5	2	2
4	I	236521	2	1.5	2	2	2	2
5	I	246411	2	2	2	2	2	2
6	I	318342	2	2	2	2	2	2
7	I	330585	2	2	2	2	2	2
8	I	236186	2	2	2	1.5	2	2
9	I	236368	2	2	2	2	2	2
10	H	234675	2	2	2	2	2	2
11	H	235964	2	2	2	2	2	2
12	H	235972	2	2	2	2	1.5	2
13	H	236344	2	2	2	2	2	2
14	H	236434	2	2	2	2	1.5+1/2	2
15	H	246394	2	2	2	1.5	1.5+1/2	2
16	H	246520	2	2	2	2	2	2
17	H	246526	2	2	2	1	2	2
18	H	246531	2	2	2	2	2	2
19	H	296680	2	2	2	1.5	2	2
20	L	320234	2	1/2	2	1.5	1.5	2
21	L	293658	2	2	2	2	2	2
22	L	184398	2	1.5	2	2	2	2
23	L	184345	1.5	1.5	2	2	2	2
24	C	178688	2	2	2	1/2	2	2
25	D	224761	1/2	2	2	1.5	1.5	2
26	D	232533	1	1.5	2	2	2	2
27	K	189962	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
28	K	294094	2	2	2	N/A	1	2
29	K	294059	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
30	K	192360	2	2	2	1	2	2
31	K	192102	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
32	K	190030	2	2	2	3	2	2
33	K	192072	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
34	K	191436	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
35	K	191418	2	2	2	2	1	3
36	G	219389	2	2	2	2	2	2
37	G	296701	2	2	2	2	3	2
38	G	235386	2	2	2	2	N/A	2

39	G	235866	2	2	2	2	N/A	3
40	G	235371	2	2	2	1	N/A	2
41	G	296688	2	2	2	2	2	2
42	G	246621	2	2	3	2	2	2
43	G	235177	2	2	1	2	2	2
44	G	211031	2	2	2	2	2	2
45	G	246682	2	2	2	2	2	2
46	J	246537	2	2	2	2	2	2
47	J	246638	1+1	2+2	2	2	2	1+1
48	J	246641	1	2	2	N/A	N/A	2
49	J	248663	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
50	J	248684	2	2	2	2	2	2
51	J	246687	1+2	2	2+2	N/A	2	2
52	J	314615	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
53	J	311090	2	2	2	2	2	2
54	J	324098	2	2	2	N/A	2	3
55	J	324124	2	2	2	2	3	3
56	A	121684	2	2	2	2	3	3
57	A	040680	2	1	2	2	3	2
58	A	122910	3	1	3	2	3	2
59	A	124259	2	2	3	3	3	3
60	A	234115	2	2	2.5	2	N/A	3
61	A	310089	3	3	3	N/A	3	N/A
62	B	244443	3	3	2.5	2	1	3
63	B	244153	2	2	3	N/A	3	N/A
64	E	233533	2	2	2	1.5	2	2
65	E	233859	2	2	2	2	1.5	2
66	E	233963	2	2	2	1.5	2	2
67	E	234687	2	2	2	2	2	2
68	E	233852	2	2	2	2	2	2
69	F	234735	2	2	2+1	2	2	1.5
70	F	219858	2	2	1	2	2	1.5
71	F	219842	2	2	2	2	2	2
72	F	199294	2	2	2	2	2	2
73	C	178781	2	2	2	2+2	2	2
74	C	119802	2	2	1.5	N/A	2	1.5
75	C	015915	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
76	C	168700	2	2	2	1.5	2	2
77	C	175439	2	2	2	N/A	2	2
78	C	178681	2	2	2	1.5	2	2

Table 3

(3 Marker) class X Mathematics SA-I 2017-2018

S. No.	Section	Student ID	Q. No. 13	Q. No. 14	Q. No. 15	Q. No. 16	Q. No. 17	Q. No. 18	Q. No. 19	Q. No. 20	Q. No. 21	Q. No. 22
1	I	246403	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
2	I	236357	1.5+1.5	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4
3	I	196003	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
4	I	236521	2.5	3	3	3	3	3	3	1.5	3	2
5	I	246411	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
6	I	318342	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
7	I	330585	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4
8	I	236186	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
9	I	236368	2.5	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3
10	H	234675	3	3	N/A	3	3	3	3	3	2	3
11	H	235964	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
12	H	235972	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
13	H	236344	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
14	H	236434	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	2.5	3	3
15	H	246394	3	3	3	3	3	2.5	3	3	3	4
16	H	246520	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
17	H	246526	3	3	2.5	3	3	3	3	2	2	3

18	H	246531	N/A	3	1.5+1/2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
19	H	296680	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	2.5	3	3
20	L	320234	2.5	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
21	L	293658	3	2.5	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
22	L	184398	2.5	3	3	3	3	3	2.5	3	3	3
23	L	184345	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
24	C	178688	2	3	3	2.5	1	3	3	1.5	N/A	3
25	D	224761	N/A	3	3	2.5	2	3	1.5	2.5	1.5	2
26	D	232533	2.5	3	3	3	3	3	1.5	3	2	1.5
27	K	189962	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2
28	K	294094	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3
29	K	294059	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	N/A	3	3
30	K	192360	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3
31	K	192102	3	3	3	N/A	3	3	2	3	3	1
32	K	190030	3	N/A	3	3	4	3	4	N/A	3.5	3
33	K	192072	2	3	3	2	3	N/A	3	3	3	4
34	K	191436	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
35	K	191418	2	3	3	3	3	3	2	4	4	4
36	G	219389	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
37	G	296701	3	3	3+3	3	3	3	1	3+4	3	N/A
38	G	235386	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3
39	G	235866	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3	5	3
40	G	235371	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	4
41	G	296688	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	4	3	3
42	G	246621	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	2	3	N/A
43	G	235177	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
44	G	211031	2	2	1	3	3	3	3	3	1+3	3
45	G	246682	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
46	J	246537	3	3	3	3	3	3+3	3	3	3	3
47	J	246638	2+1	2	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3
48	J	246641	2+1	N/A	3	3	3	3	3+1	3	3	4
49	J	248663	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3+1
50	J	248684	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
51	J	246687	3+2	3	3	3	3+1	3	3	3	3	3
52	J	314615	1+3	2	2+2	1+3	3	3	3	N/A	N/A	3+3
53	J	311090	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	3
54	J	324098	3+3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2+4	4
55	J	324124	3	3	3	2+3	3	3	N/A	4	3	4
56	A	121684	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
57	A	040680	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	4	2
58	A	122910	N/A	3	3	3+3	3+3	3	3+3	N/A	3+4+3	5
59	A	124259	3	3	3	N/A	N/A	1+2	3	N/A	N/A	N/A
60	A	234115	3	2	3	3	N/A	3	2.5	3	3	N/A
61	A	310089	N/A	3	3	N/A	3	3	3	3	4	N/A
62	B	244443	3	3	3	3	3	1	2.5	3	4	2
63	B	244153	3	3	N/A	3	N/A	4	3	3	N/A	N/A
64	E	233533	3	2+3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4+2	3
65	E	233859	2.5	2	3	3	2.5	2.5	3	3	1	2.5
66	E	233963	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	2.5	3
67	E	234687	2.5	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
68	E	233852	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3
69	F	234735	3	3	3	3	3	2+3	3	2	3	1+2
70	F	219858	2.5	3	3	3	3	2.5	3	2	N/A	3
71	F	219842	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3
72	F	199294	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	N/A	N/A	3
73	C	178781	N/A	3	3	2.5	3	3	2	1/2	1.5	4
74	C	119802	1	3	2.5	2	1.5	2	N/A	3	4	3
75	C	015915	1.5	3	2.5	3	2	2	3	2	4	3
76	C	168700	2.5	3	3	2.5	1	3	3	1.5	1	2
77	C	175439	3	3	3	2.5	2.5	2.5	3	1	1.5	2.5
78	C	178681	2	3	3	2.5	1	3	3	1.5	N/A	3

Table 4

(4 Marker) class X Mathematics SA-1 2017-20

S. No.	Section	Student ID	Q. No.23	Q. No.24	Q. No.25	Q. No.26	Q. No.27	Q. No.28	Q. No.29	Q. No.30
1	I	246403	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4
2	I	236357	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	3.5
3	I	196003	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	1+2
4	I	236521	4	4	2+4	4	4	4	4	3.5+4
5	I	246411	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	3
6	I	318342	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3
7	I	330585	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	4
8	I	236186	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4
9	I	236368	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3
10	H	234675	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	4
11	H	235964	N/A	4	2	4	4	2+4	4	4
12	H	235972	4	W/A	4	W/A	4	4	4	4
13	H	236344	4	4	4	4	W/A	4	4	4
14	H	236434	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
15	H	246394	2	3	4	4	4	N/A	3	4
16	H	246520	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
17	H	246526	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
18	H	246531	2+4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
19	H	296680	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
20	L	320234	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	4
21	L	293658	4	3.5	4	4	4	4	4	4
22	L	184398	4	3.5	4	4	4	4	4	4
23	L	184345	4	4	3.5	4	4	4	4	4
24	C	178688	4	4	4	3.5	4	N/A	4	4
25	D	224761	4	4	3.5	3	3.5	3	4	4
26	D	232533	3	1.5	2+1	3	3	3.5	4	4
27	K	189962	N/A	3	1	2	4	4	3	3
28	K	294094	N/A	4	N/A	4	4	4	3	4
29	K	294059	N/A	4	N/A	4	4	4	4	4
30	K	192360	N/A	4	N/A	4	4	2	4	4
31	K	192102	N/A	4	3	4	4	4	4	4
32	K	190030	N/A	3.5	4	4	4	N/A	4	4
33	K	192072	2	4	N/A	4	4	4	4	4
34	K	191436	N/A	3	N/A	3	4	4	4	4
35	K	191418	N/A	4	N/A	1	4	4	4	4
36	G	219389	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4
37	G	296701	6	N/A	N/A	4	4	4	4	4
38	G	235386	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	4
39	G	235866	5	4	1	W/A	4	4	4	4
40	G	235371	4	4	5	2	3	5	4	4
41	G	296688	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
42	G	246621	3	4	4+2	2	5	5	4	3
43	G	235177	3	4	4	4	2	4	4	2
44	G	211031	1+3	4	2+2	4	4	1+4	4	4
45	G	246682	4	4	2+2	3	4	4	4	4
46	J	246537	2	3	4	4	3	4	4	4
47	J	246638	N/A	4	4	4	4+2	4	4	4
48	J	246641	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4+4
49	J	248663	3	2	4	4	4	4	4	4
50	J	248684	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
51	J	246687	4	N/A	4	4	4	4	4	4
52	J	314615	N/A	4	4	4	4	4	4+4	2+4
53	J	311090	4	4	4	4	4	4	2	4
54	J	324098	4	4	4+4	4	4	N/A	N/A	N/A
55	J	324124	4	4	4	N/A	4	4	1	4
56	A	121684	4N/A	N/A	2	3	3+2+1	N/A	3	3
57	A	040680	2	2	2+1	3	2	3	1	2
58	A	122910	N/A							
59	A	124259	4	4	N/A	3	4	4	4	4

60	A	234115	4	3	2	4	4	4	3	2
61	A	310089	2	N/A	3	N/A	4	4	4	4
62	B	244443	2	2.5	1	3	2	2	2	2
63	B	244153	4	5	4	4	N/A	4	4.5	4
64	E	233533	3	3	N/A	3	N/A	1.5	N/A	4
65	E	233859	3.5	3	3.5	3	1.5	2	3.5	3.5
66	E	233963	3	3.5	3	2	2.5	1.5	4	3.5
67	E	234687	4	2	3.5	2	1	3	4	3
68	E	233852	2	3	3	3	N/A	2	4	4
69	F	234735	4	4	1	4	4	4	4	4
70	F	219858	4	4	2.5	N/A	3.5	4	1	3
71	F	219842	4	4	1.5	4	3	4	2	4
72	F	199294	4	2.5	2.5	4	1	1	4	4
73	C	178781	4	N/A	1+4	4	3	4	4	4
74	C	119802	4	3	4	3.5	4	4	3	3.5
75	C	015915	4	4	4	N/A	4	4	4	4
76	C	168700	3	1	4	3.5	4	4	4	4
77	C	175439	4	4	4	3	4	N/A	4	4
78	C	178681	4	4	4	3.5	4	N/A	4	4

Table-5

Total marks awarded to each student out of 80

S. No.	Section	Student ID	Total marks awarded out of 80
1	I	246403	78
2	I	236357	78
3	I	196003	78
4	I	236521	78
5	I	246411	78
6	I	318342	79
7	I	330585	79
8	I	236186	79
9	I	236368	79
10	H	234675	78
11	H	235964	78
12	H	235972	78
13	H	236344	78
14	H	236434	78
15	H	246394	78
16	H	246520	78
17	H	246526	78
18	H	246531	78
19	H	296680	78
20	L	320234	78
21	L	293658	78
22	L	184398	78
23	L	184345	77.5
24	C	178688	66
25	D	224761	65
26	D	232533	66
27	K	189962	65
28	K	294094	66
29	K	294059	66
30	K	192360	65
31	K	192102	65
32	K	190030	67
33	K	192072	68
34	K	191436	66
35	K	191418	69
36	G	219389	78
37	G	296701	78
38	G	235386	78
39	G	235866	79

40	G	235371	78
41	G	296688	79
42	G	246621	79
43	G	235177	78
44	G	211031	79
45	G	246682	79
46	J	246537	78
47	J	246638	78
48	J	246641	78
49	J	248663	79
50	J	248684	78
51	J	246687	78
52	J	314615	78
53	J	311090	78
54	J	324098	78
55	J	324124	79
56	A	121684	66
57	A	040680	66.5
58	A	122910	65
59	A	124259	67
60	A	234115	70
61	A	310089	65
62	B	244443	65.5
63	B	244153	65.5
64	E	233533	65
65	E	233859	65
66	E	233963	66
67	E	234687	70
68	E	233852	65
69	F	234735	74
70	F	219858	65
71	F	219842	74
72	F	199294	65
73	C	178781	68.5
74	C	119802	65
75	C	015915	66
76	C	168700	67.5
77	C	175439	69.5
78	C	178681	68.5

Analysis of re-evaluation (Table 1 to 5):

During the re-evaluation it was observed marking is done very casual manner by all the examiners. Examiners assigned marks are inflated in relation to marks achieved. But there are fewer discrepancies in respect of marking in sections C, D, E, F, H and I. But the marking has been done very carelessly by the examiners in sections A, B, G, J and K. Artificial spiking of marks is seen in many answer scripts. Marks are awarded just to stretch the score to 78 or 79 out of 80. Following discrepancies has been observed:

- A question has been attempted by the examinee 2 or 3 times. All the attempts have been awarded by the examiners and also added by him/her in the grand total just to award the examinee 78 or 79 marks, where as in most of cases examinees do not deserve 78 or 79 marks.
- Graph is not drawn by the students in question no. 25 yet they have been awarded full marks in that question.
- In few cases question carries only 3 marks and awarded marks are 4. Similarly question carries only 2 marks and 3 marks are awarded by the examiners.
- Wrong attempts are also awarded full marks
- If an examinee has not even attempted 3 to 5 five questions out of 30 questions, still his /her score is 78 or 79 how is it possible?
- Over all result is 7.78 % only.
- Examiners are awarding floating marks.
- Most of these examiners are guest teachers.

Case study school -2

One of Self-assessment strategies in the classroom: Adopted school: Vidyalya-A, Class 9th, Sections A to I

Subject: Mathematics.

- Dated 6th Jan2018: discussion with students about their performance in the Mid-term exam2017-2018 and difficulties and strategies to improve their scores.
- Start of the self-assessment process.
- Periodic test of math was held on 8 Jan 2018.
- All the students were asked to prepare a self-analysis chart on the following format.
- PTM (Parent Teachers Meeting) was held on 27th January 2018.

Periodic Test Self-analysis (Tool)

Name of student: -----Class & Section: -----

Question Number	Marks allotted	Marks scored/ not attempted
1	1	
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7	2	
8		
9		
10		
11		
12		
13	3	
14		
15		
16		
17		
18		
19		
20		
21		
22		
23		

24	4	
25		
26		
27		
28		
29		
30		
Total-30	Total 80	Total

Also students were asked to select 10 chapters of their choice out of total 15 chapters. Then the relation between scores of self-assessed questions and chapters will be finding out in the next visit discussion. Will try to find out the strategies to improve the scores and on which lesson and how each one of them should work more would also be chalk out.

Table -6

Periodic Test January 2018

Class 9th

Subject Mathematics

Abbreviations used in the table: "N" - Not Attempted, "-" "Not mentioned.

Section	IX C										IX B										IX F				
S.No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
Roll No.	2	10	19	23	24	30	31	33	35	40	41	45	46	9	15	21	27	30	36	44	4	12	18	34	46
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	-	1	1	1
2	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1/2	1	1	0	1	1	N	1	1	0	-	1	-	-	0
3	1	1	0	1	1	0	N	N	1	0	N	0	0	1	1	1	1	N	0	0	1/2	1	1	-	1
4	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1/2	0	N	1	0	1	0	0	1	1/2	-	1	0
5	1	1/2	1/2	0	1	1/2	1/2	N	1	1/2	1/2	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1/2	0	-	-	1/2	1.5	-
6	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1/2	0	1/2	1/2	N	1/2	1	1	N	0	0	-	1	1	-	-
7	2	2	1	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	N	1.5	1	N	1	N	0	0	0	0	-	1	-	-	-
8	2	1.5	0	0	2	0	N	0	2	N	0	2	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	1	-	1	-	-	-
9	2	1/2	0	0	2	1	N	0	N	0	N	2	1/2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	-	-	1	1.5	-
10	1	0	2	1.5	2	1	1	1	2	0	1	1	1	0	N	1	1	1	0	0	-	-	1	1	-
11	1	1.5	0	N	2	0	0	0	2	0	1/2	0	0	0	0	N	0	0	1/2	0	-	-	1	-	-
12	2	1	1/2	0	2	1/2	1/2	0	2	1	N	0	0	0	1/2	2	0	2	N	0	2	2	2	-	-
13	3	N	0	1/2	1/2	1	0	N	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1/2	0	-	3	1	-	-
14	3	1/2	3	3	2	1	N	0	3	0	2	3	1/2	0	0	1	0	N	0	0	2	2.5	2	-	-
15	3	1/2	N	N	0	1.5	0	1/2	3	0	N	3	1	N	0	3	0	3	0	0	-	-	1	-	-
16	1.5	2.5	1/2	1/2	3	3	1/2	1/2	1	1	1	3	1	0	1	3	N	N	1/2	0	-	-	-	-	-
17	3	3	3	N	3	3	2	0	3	0	3	3	3	1.5	1.5	3	2.5	2.5	3	2	1/2	3	3	-	-
18	N	1/2	N	N	N	1	N	1/2	3	0	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-
19	2.5	1	1/2	1/2	1/2	2	1/2	0	3	1	1/2	3	0	0	N	3	0	0	1/2	0	-	-	1	3	-
20	2.5	1	1.5	0	2	2	N	0	3	0	1/2	2	N	N	1.5	3	0	N	0	0	1	-	-	-	-
21	3	1	1/2	0	N	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	0	N	0	0	0	1	N	0	0	1.5	0	-	-	3	-	-
22	2	1/2	1	0	0	1	N	0	3	0	N	1.5	N	N	0	2	N	N	0	0	-	-	-	-	1
23	1	2	N	N	0	0	0	1/2	4	0	N	4	N	0	0	0	N	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-
24	2	N	0	1.5	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	1.5	N	N	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-
25	4	1.5	0	1	1.5	4	0	0	4	1	0	2	1	0	1	4	4	4	0	0	4	4	-	-	-
26	N	N	1	0	N	0	N	N	2	0	0	1/2	N	N	1	0	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-
27	3.5	1	N	1/2	N	2	1	1.5	4	1	1	1	1	0	N	4	N	N	1	0	1	-	-	-	-
28	1	1	1/2	0	N	1	1	0	4	0	1	1	N	0	1	N	N	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-
29	N	N	0	0	N	1/2	N	N	3.5	0	N	3.5	N	N	0	4	N	4	4	0	-	-	1	-	-
30	2	1	N	0	1	1	1	N	3.5	0	1	4	N	0	0	0	N	N	0	0	4	-	2.5	-	-
Total	52	29	16	13	31	30	9	13	71	6	13	47	13	3	12	45	12	22	11	3	16	21	29	7	3

Table -7

Abbreviations used in the table: "N" Not seen

S.No.	Section	Roll No.	Marks In Mid term	Marks in Periodic test
1	I	1	4	2
2	I	2	10	10
3	I	6	6	1
4	I	14	14	6
5	I	21	6	1
6	I	30	5	9
7	I	33	11	9
8	I	37	22	20
9	I	39	2	1
10	I	40	9	2
11	I	45	6	2
12	I	46	6	N
13	F	2	8	12
14	F	4	20	16
15	F	7	4	12
16	F	11	14	21
17	F	13	7	3
18	F	14	8	12
19	F	18	19	29
20	F	27	2	1
21	F	31	22	7
22	F	43	6	3
23	B	2	20	13
24	B	3	11	N
25	B	7	5	2
26	B	9	5	3
27	B	15	12	12
28	B	18	9	8
29	B	19	11	8
30	B	21	48	45
31	B	24	0	31
32	B	26	4	5
33	B	27	9	11
34	B	30	19	22
35	B	33	1	6
36	B	35	0	2
36	B	36	3	4
37	B	37	9	8
38	B	38	8	N
39	B	40	14	10
40	B	43	8	3
41	B	45	0	4
42	B	47	2	N
43	B	48	4	0
44	B	49	0	5
45	B	50	9	2
46	B	51	1	1
47	C	1	2	N
48	C	2	49	52
49	C	3	28	18
50	C	4	28	8
51	C	5	10	3
52	C	6	13	10
53	C	7	28	27
54	C	8	10	12
55	C	9	14	N
56	C	10	21	29
57	C	11	42	33
58	C	12	21	16
59	C	13	7	N
60	C	14	8	N
61	C	16	11	7
62	C	17	18	16
63	C	19	18	16
64	C	20	15	9
65	C	22	43	37
66	C	23	18	13

67	C	25	10	8
68	C	27	7	6
69	C	28	25	30
70	C	29	11	18
71	C	30	4	30
72	C	31	9	30
73	C	32	7	10
74	C	33	13	7
75	C	35	62	71
76	C	36	9	11
77	C	37	16	16
78	C	40	15	6
79	C	41	12	13
80	C	42	7	8
81	C	43	9	6
82	C	44	13	6
83	C	45	31	47
84	C	46	14	7
85	C	47	10	6
86	C	48	18	12
87	C	49	17	7
88	C	50	22	17
89	C	51	8	13
90	C	53	9	14
91	C	54	12	5
92	C	55	26	27
93	C	56	22	13
94	C	57	29	18
95	C	59	25	29
96	C	61	18	27
97	C	62	13	17
98	C	63	12	8
99	C	66	22	38
100	C	67	11	12

Analysis:

- Out of 470 students in all, 25 could respond to this self-assessment form (Table 6).
- 100 students could tell about their scores in the mathematics.(Table 7)
- Students could not even tell exact numbers of questions, design of question paper in the periodic test and how many questions carry 1 mark and how many carry 2 marks.
- In one of the sections examiner has only announced the marks and answer scripts after evaluation are not even shown to them.
- Follow up of the test is just formality to write the answers in note book for both teachers and students.
- No marks for the steps in the questions are given to the examinees.
- No question paper design was discussed in the class neither before the periodic test nor after the periodic test.
- Results of Mid Term Exam and Periodic Test don't differ significantly.
- Presence of students in all the sections after the Periodic test is very thin. It seems that students do not want to face the situation where they are declared failure by the school authorities.
- Till the final exam teachers try to convey that child is not ready for the exam and student try to convey that he is ready with what the system has given to him.
- Over all pass % is 1.75%. which may lead to the situations:
 1. Where students have to stop their studies.
 2. Frustration of students and parents may results into Suicide and killing of teachers and principals and destruction of schools' property.

Both the cases are extreme and force us to think on the following points.

1. Why do the examiners need to do all this?
2. Why the children are so casual about their studies that there was 3 to 4 months gap between both the exams (Mid Term and Periodic Exam) yet there no significant change in the scores of the students in the mathematics subject.
3. What kind of assessment system should we have?
4. Do in-service teachers need some training about the assessment processes also?

5. Do we need to introduce assessment for learning with assessment of learning?
6. Do our classroom strategies should be aligned with assessment for learning.

Observation of the above case studies leads us to think about assessment for learning also with assessment of learning in the existing assessment pattern.

Effect of self- reflection activity (Periodic Test Self-Analysis):

1. This activity helped the students and teachers to frame **SMART** targets.
2. During the PTM teachers guided the students and parents about SMART strategies for the final exams.
3. Peer feedback strategy **using Model and Exemplar** was also used by one of the teacher. He asked the other students to study the answer script of the top scorer of the class.
4. **Learning targets** (lessons which can help the students to score passing marks: coordinate Geometry, linear equation, construction, central tendencies, probability etc.) were discussed by the teachers with the students and parents.

Suggestive classroom strategies and tools for assessment for learning:

A number of classroom strategies that are particularly effective in promoting assessment for learning practice and to make classroom more creative. Also these are helpful for teachers to control the classroom behaviour of the children and to achieve the learning out comes.

1. **Use of questioning. 2. Peer feedback. 3. Student self-assessment. 4. Formative use of summative assessment.**
 1. **Use of questioning:** questioning is used not only as a pedagogical tool but also as deliberate way for the teacher to find out what students know understand and are able to do. Teacher feedback focuses on establishing success criteria and tells students what they have achieved and why they need to improve? Teacher can use in order to decide grouping. What to teach next and in what order?

Strategies:

Preparing key questions (regarding learning outcome) what were the key questions that you wanted the students to be able to answer at the end of the lesson

Distributing questions of required learning outcome around the class

Hands down. What is the link that teachers see between wait times and hands down?

Wait of thinking time. What are the circumstances under which the teacher provide their students with wait time or thinking time?

Building on "wrong answers". What are the some ways in which teachers make use of inappropriate answers from students?

Promoting students to further responses. What kind of further responses?

Responding positively to the students answers. Responses are valued and to build motivation and self-esteem.

Encouraging students to ask questions. What formative use can be made of the questions asked by the students? Asking closed questions and purpose of the closed question. Asking open questions. What kind of open questions can you ask?

Link between questioning and assessment for learning.

2. **Peer feedback:** peer feedback occurs when a student uses established success criteria to tell another student what they have achieved and where improvement is necessary. Strategies particularly suited to younger students, teachers have for these strategies provide a “short hand” way of communicating to student that they wish them to provide peer feedback.

Examples:

- a. **Two stars and a wish** (two positive aspects of the peer work and a wish to improve).

- b. **Plus, minus and what next?**(What was done in relation to success criteria, and also what could be done better?)

- c. **Warm and cool feedback** (positive feedback is warm feedback, identify areas that need improvement is cool feedback)

- d. **Traffic lights** (using highlighters on the margin of the work when the work is in progress. Or coloured sticky notes on the final work).

Suggestions: would then relate to the next occasion on which the students undertook work, which required similar skills- writing or number skills, for example.

- e. **Using models or exemplar:** Teachers demonstrate for students how they can match the work of a peer to an exemplar, for example:- handwriting
(Letters on/off line, straight/crooked letters, no spaces/spaces between words, mixture of upper and lower letters etc.)

[Type a quote from the document or the summary of an interesting point. You can position the text box anywhere in the document. Use the Text Box Tools tab to change the formatting of the pull quote text box.]

Students explain to the peer why they have selected this particular exemplar and using other exemplar, explain what peer needs to do in order to improve his/her hand writing. Exemplar of various products (written and 3D can be displayed in the classroom for use both by individual to self- assess and also by peers to provide basic feedback.

- f. **De Bono’s thinking Hats:** thinking hats encourage thinking from different perspectives. They can be used to focus student’s feedback to their peers. Teacher model the use of the thinking hats and train the students in their use before asking them to use hats as one of the peer feedback strategy. Like: Black Hat, Green Hat and Yellow Hat.

Black Hat Urges caution and evaluation "Is this true? what are the weaknesses?	Green Hat Encourages creative thinking 'Is there another way of doing this? What would be better? How else can this be done?	Yellow Hat Encourage students to think about the "good point" to ask themselves questions such as "Why will this work"

Giving different students different hats can make peer feedback more focused and manageable for younger students. That way, each individual does not have to consider every aspect of the peer feedback but can concentrate on just one.

Peer Assessment (reflection activity)		
Please rate your peer by writing the number that corresponds best with her/his performance during the sessions.	Ratings 1. Never 2. Occasionally 3. Sometimes 4. Frequently 5. always	
Name-----Date-----Class-----Name of peer-----		
<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>Rating</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
<i>Stayed on task</i>		
<i>Worked well with others</i>		
<i>Listened to others</i>		
<i>Contributed ideas</i>		
<i>Encouraged others</i>		
<i>Is an asset to group</i>		
Comment		

3. self-assessment:

In classrooms where assessment for learning is practised, students are encouraged to be more active in their learning and associated assessment. The ultimate purpose of assessment for learning is to create self-learning regulated learners who can leave the school able and confident to continue leaning throughout their lives.

To enhance the student assessment strategies are

- a. Use of rubrics and setting of goals or learning outcomes
- b. Reflection activity
- c. Student led and three way conference
- d. Use of graphic organiser and group assessment

a. **Use of rubrics and setting of goals and learning outcomes:** The setting of learning outcomes or goal setting is an intrinsic part of the iterative nature of self-assessment. Student self-assessment begins with setting learning outcomes, proceeds through the production of work that aims to achieve those outcomes,

to the assessment of the work to see if it does in fact meet the targets and then, finally, to the setting of new outcomes or revised ones, that were not achieved.

Student will assume responsibility for the setting of their learning outcomes and also for the monitoring or tracking of these outcomes. Students’ ability to do this will vary, and teacher assistance will be more important to some students. Teacher commonly can use the SMART acronym as a way of guiding students in the design of learning outcomes in this acronym:

b. **Reflection activity:** Teachers can use Performa to encourage the students to reflect on their learning experience. While these are convenient and provide a record of student thinking.

<i>Self- Assessment (Reflection activity)</i>		
<i>Please rate yourself by writing the number that corresponds best with the performance during the sessions.</i>	Ratings 1. Never 2. Occasionally 3. Sometimes 4. Frequently 5. always	
Name-----Date-----Class-----		
Descriptors	Rating	Remarks

<i>I was able to Stay focused on various tasks.</i>		
<i>I am able to work well with the group.</i>		
<i>I am a cooperative member of the group.</i>		
<i>I Contributed ideas to the group</i>		
<i>I completed my portion of task well.</i>		
<i>I completed my portion of task on time.</i>		
<i>Comment</i>		

- c. **Student led three way conferences:** A conference in which students present their learning to their teacher and parents are an opportunity for students to formally reflect on the learning that has taken place over the period of time. This reflection occurs as students prepare for the conference, as well as during the conference itself when they show and explain to their parents what they have learned. Mental math quiz, model exhibition, project presentations, talks in the assembly on selected topics etc. It helps the child to build up self-esteem not only in front of the teachers but also in front of their parents and peers. it also motivates the child for further learning and boosts his/her confidence level.
- d. **Use of graphic organiser and Group assessment:**

Group- Assessment (Reflection Activity)		
<i>Please rate your group by writing the number that corresponds best with its performance during the sessions.</i>	Ratings 1. Never 2. Occasionally 3. Sometimes 4. Frequently 5. always	
<i>Name-----Date-----Class-----</i>		
Descriptors	Rating	Remarks
<i>I was able to Stay focused on various tasks.</i>		
<i>I am able to work well with the group.</i>		
<i>I am a cooperative member of the group.</i>		
<i>I Contributed ideas to the group</i>		
<i>I completed my portion of task well.</i>		
<i>I completed my portion of task on time.</i>		
<i>Comment</i>		

Strategies to promote the formative use of tests:

- a. Making use of results from state and national testing for example **base line test** of Directorate of Education (DOE) Delhi. It has two aspects: preparing students for tests and making use of tests results.
- b. Making formative use of classroom testing for example **weekly tests** (DOE), before the tests.
- c. **Timings of tests:**
 1. **Before the lesson/unit test**-test administered at the beginning of the lesson/unit can be an accurate way of determining exactly what students already know and are able to do. This information is then used to shape the approach to the teaching of the topic and to identify a starting point for further learning.
 2. **Mid-way test**- A test mid-way through a lesson/unit is another way test can be used by both students and teachers for assessment for learning purpose. Gaps in understanding are revealed in a timely fashion, allowing teachers to focus teaching to fit student needs and provide students with the opportunity to act on feedback to improve their performance.
 3. **After the test**-after the test, there are many opportunities for a formative approach. Instead of simply handing back the marked tests to students and then going through the test to explain the required answers, teachers can use strategies which encourage further reinforcement and learning.
 Before the test is marked and returned to the students, the teacher divides up the test and allots different sections of questions to groups of students. The role of the students is to agree on a response to each of the questions and how marks should be allotted. Groups then share their work with the class.

Teachers identify those questions which caused the most difficulty for students, and then go over the answers to these with the class before they return the completed tests to the students.

Teachers identify the toughest questions they ask students to review those questions in pairs to confirm what they believe should be the correct answers. They then confirm their answers with another pair before checking with the teacher. (This strategies was suggested by the Alberta Assessment consortium).

d. Preparing for the test using traffic lights:

The resulting record gives students a focus on their revision for final test.

So, classroom strategies that are particularly effective in promoting assessment for learning practice such as Use of questioning, Peer feedback, Student self-assessment and Formative use of summative assessment should be according to changing nature of educational goals as well as with the cordial relationship between assessment and the teaching learning.

References:

1. NIE Singapore learning, (*Teaching and Mentoring Program Run -3 by DOE of GNCT of Delhi*).
2. Assessment for learning website by *Curriculum Corporation of Australia*.
3. *Assessing Student Outcomes by Robert J. Marzano, Debra Pickering and Jay McTighe*.